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Research Article

EVALUATION OF THYROID FUNCTION IN β - THALASSEMIA MAJOR PATIENTS AT TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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Abstract:

Objective: To determine the status of thyroid function among β -thalassemia major patients dependent on transfusion.

Material And Methods: This descriptive, cross sectional analysis was conducted at Dept. of Pathology (Hematology) - Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences, Jamshoro and Thalassemia Centre Hyderabad upon a sample of 114 pre-diagnosed patients of either gender aged 5 and above and suffering from Beta Thalassemia with history of recurrent blood transfusions (more than 20 transfusions or a transfusion history of more than 2 years), chosen via non-probability - consecutive sampling. The laboratory results were recorded onto a pre-structured questionnaire after taking written informed consent. Data obtained was analyzed using SPSS v. 16. 0 and MS. Excel 360.

Results: Among the total 114 patients studied, a majority comprised of females. The mean age, TSH level and FT4 of the sample stood at 12.38 (± 5.71 SD) years, 3.53 ($+3.67$ SD) and 1.34 ($+1.16$ SD) respectively. An interesting association between serum ferritin level and history of extensive blood transfusions, especially when the transfusions roughly exceeded 300 ($P = 0.003$).

Conclusion: After careful consideration, it can be concluded that Hypothyroidism is common among transfusion dependent β -thalassemia major patients.

Key Words: β Thalassemia Major, Blood Transfusion, Endocrinopathy, Hypothyroidism and Serum Ferritin.

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INTRODUCTION:

Beta-thalassemia is an inherited autosomal recessive disorder much more prevalent in Pakistan. ¹ Annually around 0.1 million more children with the thalassemia disease are brought into this world and at present nearly 0.240 billion beta thalassemia carriers walk among us. ² In this part of the globe, the beta thalassemia carrier rate goes up to eight percent among people hailing from socio-demographics and all ethnicities. ³

Increased incidence of thalassemia has been repeatedly noted the Middle East, the South-East Asian region and the Far East. ⁴ Iron is deposited in most tissues of the body including the heart, liver and the endocrine glands. Due to iron sedimentation, various common endocrine complications occur in transfusion dependent thalassemia patients, which may ultimately result in much morbidity (organ damage) and mortality. ⁵

Decrease thyroid hormones production or defective receptors of thyroid hormone lead to hypothyroidism which occurs by gland infiltration, free radical injury, chronic tissue hypoxia and organ siderosis. ⁶ Central hypothyroidism is caused by decreased secretion, from the anterior pituitary gland, of Thyrotrophin Stimulating Hormone (TSH) or by low secretion from the hypothalamus from Thyrotrophin Releasing Hormone (TRH).⁷ In several studies, correlation of low thyroid level with serum ferritin level has been reported; although in some studies there were no such correlations. In contrast to significant iron deposition in thyroid gland, low activity remains about subclinical hypothyroidism. ⁸

Hypothyroidism is a most common complication of the endocrine system in the twenties of life in thalassemia major (TM) patients, requiring recurrent and frequent blood transfusion. ⁹ Clinical hypothyroidism manifests as lethargy, cold intolerance, decreased appetite, weight gain etc. The objective of this study was to determine thyroid function status in patients suffering from transfusion dependent Beta thalassemia major Patients above the age of 5 years.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This descriptive, cross sectional analysis was conducted at Dept. of Pathology (Hematology) - Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences, Jamshoro and Thalassemia Centre Hyderabad from upon a sample of 114 individuals.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Age 5 – 35 years.
2. Diagnosed cases of β -thalassemia major with recurrent blood transfusion.
3. Both genders were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Congenital hypothyroidism and goiter.
2. History of prior use of medications that may affect or modulate endocrine function
3. Pancreatic tumors/annular pancreas.

In a complete aseptic way, sim milliliter of blood is collected using labelled, standard tube used for sampling. Thermostat scientific Machine HERAEUS LABOFUGE 400 used for centrifugation of sample for 10-15 minutes at 2500 RPM and after that , it was analyzed through Electrochemi-illuminescence Immuno assay (ECLIA) performed on Cobas e 6000 series (cobas e 601) by Roche Hitachi. The laboratory results were recorded onto a pre-structured questionnaire after taking written informed consent. Data obtained was analyzed using SPSS v. 16. 0 and MS. Excel 360.

RESULTS:

Among the total one hundred and fourteen patients studied. The mean age of the sample stood at 12.38 (± 5.71 SD) years, with a total range of 30 years. Predominance of female was found about 56.1% and male were found 43.9%.

GRAPH.1 Gender Distribution

The mean of ferritin level stood at 5183.69 ng/ml (SD \pm 240.95). Mean TSH level was 3.53 μ U/ml (SD+3.67). Mean of FT4 was found 1.34 μ U/ml (SD+1.16). An interesting association between serum ferritin level and history of extensive blood transfusions, especially when the transfusions roughly exceeded 300 (P = 0.003).

Table: No. 1 Ferritin versus Number of Transfusions.

Variables	No. of transfusion				P-value
	1-100	101-200	201-300	>300	
Ferritin level	3832.5 \pm 1573.1	4522.9 \pm 1617.1	5300.4 \pm 2652.9	6090.5 \pm 2514.4	0.003

No any noticeable difference was noted between the mean FT4 and TSH levels in relationship with the transfusion rate with P value of greater than 0.05 in each.9.71 and 0.151 respectively.

Table: No. 2 TSH and FT4 level with No. of Transfusion

Variables	No. of transfusion				P-value
	1-100	101-200	201-300	>300	
TSH	03.14 \pm 2.22	03.00 \pm 1.66	02.82 \pm 1.54	04.60 \pm 5.60	0.151
FT4	1.36 \pm 0.22	1.30 \pm 0.19	1.27 \pm 0.14	1.40 \pm 1.97	9.71

DISCUSSION:

B-thalassemia major is among the commonest congenital hemoglobinopathies around the world. In multi-transfused thalassemia patients, the most common secondary complications include iron overload and growth retardation. Therefore, effective iron chelation and close monitoring of iron burden is crucial in these patients.

The mean ferritin level among the sample stood at 5183.69 ng/ml (\pm 240.95 SD) in our study while

others such as Karunaratna AM et al ¹⁰ have reported lower mean serum ferritin concentrations i.e. 2992.2 ng/ml, (\pm 1575.35 SD). In addition to that, others too have researched this aspect and found results synonymous to our findings, examples being studies conducted in Middle East, ¹¹ the sub-continent ¹² and even specifically in Pakistan ¹³ reporting mean serum ferritin levels of be 3272.5 ng/ml , 6723 ng/ml and 4236.5 ng/ml respectively.

In present study, it is shown that a very few patients are suffering from thyroid dysfunction (hypothyroidism). Mean of TSH level was 3.53 ± 3.67 and mean of FT4 was found 1.34 ± 1.16 . In the comparison of our study the mean of TSH level and FT4 is 6.38 ± 0.83 mIU/ml, 1.08 ± 0.45 ng/dl respectively in Suraj Haridas et al⁶ and 12.6 ± 4.6 in the study of Fatima I et al¹⁴ which is higher than our study while in another study by A. G. Pirinççioğlu et al shows normal thyroid profile in study participants.¹⁵

In the study of Fatima et al, the prevalence of hypothyroidism reported (13.5%) in β -thalassemia patients.¹⁴ Other researchers too have claimed approximately similar findings from Iran (up to 15%)^{16, 17}, Oman (19%)¹⁸, China (11%)¹⁹ and Greece (14%)²⁰. Our study reports a relatively lower prevalence of hypothyroidism and this is attributable to fact that this study comprised of a significant number of patients belonging to the pediatric group and had fewer transfusions.

CONCLUSION:

After careful consideration, it can be rightly concluded that various endocrine dysfunctions are common in thalassemia patients. Hypothyroidism was most frequent. The interesting relationship between serum ferritin level and recurrent transfusion merits to be explored further.

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